

Quantum Resolution and Local versus Global Equilibrium

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 9, 2021

Newtonian mechanics is based on local information and derivatives. Quantum particles like electrons, however, seem to have a “built-in” resolution mechanics related to their wavelength which in turn is related to momentum. In order to have resolution in space of the order $1/p$, it seems one must have a spatial density hump of this order. Thus, there is a probability-like function describing the electron wavelength. As a result, it does not seem that one may use a local treatment and take derivatives to calculate acceleration. If one considers translation of a quantum particle to be equivalent to a 2×2 rotation matrix in $\cos(px)$, then a two-vector $(\cos(px), \sin(px))$ is a solution. Its modulus maps to a constant which removes all sense of momentum dependent resolution and yields resolution at each x point i.e. classical physics.

Classical statistical mechanics is also a local theory. For a quantum particle with resolution based on wavelength $1/p$, it seems that a statistical theory should be global i.e. based on $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, a distribution $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ is created, but even this picture is too simple. Various $\exp(ip_j x)$'s may combine with portions of $V(x)$ to form $\exp(ipx)$. This distribution should be related to physical observables and it is as $a(p)a(p)$ is the probability to obtain a particle with momentum p from within the entire x range. Thus, an equilibrium is established between global free particle wavefunctions and a potential which is also broken into a global scheme $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$.

At the same time, it seems global probabilities should be able to create a local statistical picture which they do i.e. $E = V(x) + [\sum_p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx)] / [\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)]$ which leads to classical type quantities. These local averages are also measurable i.e. $V(x)$ and $W(x)W(x)$ for a bound system. The idea of resolution carries over into the average with a physical spatial distribution (i.e. humps and troughs) being present (although not in the form of $\cos(px)$) to represent a kind of periodic behaviour.

The local statistical picture deals in averages and does not show the exact interaction of $V(x)$ with $\exp(ipx)$'s. This is also the case of the quantum average $\langle W | \text{Operator} | W \rangle$ which is a product of averages i.e. $W W \{ \text{Operator} W / W \}$. Thus, the classical local scenario may be a simplified average picture.

Free Quantum Particle and Locality

Assume a quantum particle contains a built-in mechanism related to a spatial resolution of $1/p$ where p is momentum, as demonstrated by two slit interference experiments on electrons. Classically, a free particle has no fixed resolution, it may be at any x point in Newtonian mechanics. The two views may be mapped into each other. One may consider a 2×2 rotation matrix acting on a two vector to create a translation:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} \cos(p dx) & -\sin(p dx) \\ \sin(p dx) & \cos(p dx) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} |a(px)| \\ |b(px)| \end{pmatrix} &= \exp(i dx d/dx) \begin{pmatrix} |a(px)| \\ |b(px)| \end{pmatrix} \quad ((1)) \end{aligned}$$

A solution is $a(px)=\cos(px)$ and $b(px)=\sin(px)$ or $\exp(ipx)$. This describes a wavelength related to $1/p$, but the modulus is 1 linking to classical physics which is local i.e. the electron may be at each x point. In such a case, one may consider Newtonian mechanics, but for the resolution picture which seems to require a spatial density linked to the wavelength in order to manifest the resolution in space a statistical approach seems more appropriate as it manifests itself in experiments.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

Classical statistical mechanics is local. For a gas, particles with different momenta scatter elastically in two body reactions to maintain an equilibrium based on temperature T i.e. average kinetic energy. There is no concept of wavelength for the particles so it is fine to have them exist at a point. By matching scattering reaction probabilities with their time reversed scenarios i.e. $f(p_1)f(p_2)=f(p_3)f(p_4)$ and $p_1p_1/2m + p_2p_2/2m = p_3p_3/2m + p_4p_4/2m$ one finds that $f(p)$ proportional to $\exp(-pp/2mT)$. If a potential $V(x)$ is present, this same argument holds at each x , so probability seems to be separable. Moreover, in dx , $V(x)$ changes the kinetic energy of each $pip_i/2m$ by the same amount, so the overall probability is $\exp(-pp/2mT -V(x)/T)$. Thus, one has a local theory with $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ space dependent weights which lead to changing density. A free particle with momentum p_1 has different probability magnitudes to be at different x points. There is no idea of a fixed modulus as in the case of the free quantum particle.

It may be noted that classical statistical mechanics gives both momentum distributions and spatial distributions. For the momentum distribution, one may define an operator which yields average kinetic energy i.e.

$$\text{Sum over } p \ C \exp(-V(x)/T) \ pp/2m \ exp(-pp/2mT) = \ exp(-V(x)/T) \ \text{Sum over } p \ (C (2mTT) \ d/dp \ d/dp + 2mT) \ exp(-pp/2mT) \ \text{((1))}$$

Thus, the idea of using operators is not really unique to quantum mechanics, although in quantum mechanics one may have a wavefunction $W(x)$ whose $-1/2m \ d/dx \ d/dx \ W(x) / W(x)$ yields $KE(x)$ because of the link of momentum p to wavelength and the global nature of the probability.

Global Quantum Equilibrium

For a quantum particle in a potential $V(x)$, one has resolution i.e. wavelength related to $1/p$ and so cannot use Newtonian mechanics which takes derivatives at each x . Thus, a statistical approach may be tried with the potential rendering momentum hits which change a p_1 into a p_2 etc. This already leads to very different physics from Newtonian mechanics. One may write:

$$V(x)= \text{Sum over } k \ V(k) \ exp(ikx) \ \text{((2))}$$

and suggest that $\exp(ikx)$ yields a momentum hit of k . As a result, a momentum state of p may be created by any pi interacting with a $p-pi=k$ piece of $V(x)$. $V(x)$ is then taken to be an average quantity, although measurable. It is important to note that there is no concept of work here as

there is no locality. Thus, it is not clear what $V(x)$ means except for the fact that it can give momentum hits. Furthermore, there is no concept of kinetic energy $pp/2m$ because this also comes from Newtonian mechanics which is local. Nevertheless, an equilibrium must be established between the various global $\exp(ipx)$ interacting with $V(x)$. In addition, this global result for each $\exp(ipx)$ should average to give a local picture in which there is $V(x)$ and a local $W(x)$ based on the interference of the various $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ terms as well as kinetic energy.

We thus suggest that kinetic energy may be ultimately related to a rotation-resolution mechanism for a free particle described by $\exp(ipx)$. This particle has a momentum of p and a kinetic energy of $pp/2m$, but does not really follow Newtonian mechanics. It only follows Newtonian mechanics if one ignores the resolution. In such a case, one has a momentum p and KE of $pp/2m$ from Newtonian physics, but it seems that $pp/2m$ may have deeper roots. Thus, in establishing a global equilibrium one may suggest:

$$a(p) pp/2m \exp(ipx) + \text{Sum over } k \ V(k) a(p-k) \exp(ipx) = E(p) a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

One has explicit interactions of portions of the potential with various $\exp(i(p-i)x)$, something which does not happen in classical mechanics. One may note that $E(p)$ appears on the RHS of ((3)). If an equilibrium is established the various $a(p)$ values may adjust to make $E(p)=E$ for all p . In such a case one has a loss of information or equilibrium. Thus, each free particle with momentum p has kinetic energy $pp/2m$, but there is an additional free particle energy associated with different $\exp(ipjx)$'s converting to p , so the overall energy is E . The $a(p)$'s are not simply mathematical coefficients. One may make global statistical measurements by trying to capture the quantum particle from the bound $V(x)$ system. In such a case, $a(p)a(p)$ is the probability to find the particle in state p anywhere in the x range and this is measurable.

The various global $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ described in the equilibrium equation ((3)) should form an average to yield a local picture. Given that each $\exp(ipx)$ has spatial resolution, it seems the idea of spatial resolution does not disappear even in the local scenario:

$$KE(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) pp/2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x) = -1/2m d/dx d/dx W / W \quad ((4))$$

Thus, the idea of humps and troughs remains, but one has locality in ((4)) i.e. $KE(x)$ which is the classical value.

When taking the average of $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ probabilities something interesting occurs. One creates a new overall resolution system with its own periodic-rotation type scenario i.e. humps and troughs i.e. $W(x)$. $W(x)W(x)$ gives the spatial density which is measurable. It seems that a resolution scheme governs density in all cases. The actual mechanism of interference is confusing. For example, if one simply had $\cos(px)$, both the negative and positive regions upon squaring would yield the same spatial density results. If one adds $\cos(p1x) + \cos(p2x)$, there may be positive and negative regions partially canceling (interfering) to produce lower spatial density in some regions. Thus, it seems an overall resolution pattern (i.e. local) governs local density, yet it may be "made" of global $\exp(ipx)$ resolution patterns which interfere. It should, however, be noted that one does not simply have $\exp(ipx)a(p)$ which interfere i.e. $\text{Sum over } a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Rather, various $\exp(ip1x)$'s interact with portions of $V(x)$ to create a much more complicated equilibrium picture as given in ((3)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum free particles such as electrons have a built-in kind of resolution mechanism giving rise to a wavelength proportional to $1/p$. This has the appearance of a statistical spatial type density because one cannot have uniform density in order to detect lengths of $1/p$. Given this resolution linked to momentum, it seems one cannot apply Newton's equations which apply to each point in space. Thus, a statistical approach is used assuming $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle i.e. a global probability unlike the local ones used in classical statistical mechanics. This means that the potential must interact globally, changing one global p_1 into another. $V(x)$ is taken as an average of $\text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx)$ with V_k giving a hit of k to a p_1 converting it to p_1+k . As a result, an $\exp(ipx)$ is not really free in the sense that a $V_k \exp(ikx)$ may combine with an $\exp(i(p-k)x)$ to form $\exp(ipx)$. A complicated statistical cycling occurs which we call an equilibrium and suggest that: $a(p) p p/2m \exp(ipx) + \text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k a(p-k) \exp(ipx) = a(p) E \exp(ipx)$.

At the global level, it seems there is no sense of $p p/2m$ (kinetic energy) or work. These are local concepts. Nevertheless, if one insists that an averaging of the global equilibrium give rise to local statistical averages which then follow Newton's law, one may use $p p/2m$ although it may arise from the resolution/wavelength nature of a quantum particle and only appear at the average level in classical physics.

As a result, one has the average equation: $E = V(x) - 1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$. $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$ seems like a simple "interfering" average, but we argue that the complicated interaction of all $\exp(ip_j x)$ with V_k 's etc really occurs. In both the global scenario and local $W(x)$, kinetic energy is given by $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$, but the local one changes with x like in classical physics. Both the local and global pictures must be maintained because both give rise to physical observables. An interaction may knock the particle out of the bound state and it will have a probability $a(p)a(p)$ to be in state p and may have come from any x . Alternatively, $W(x)W(x)$ gives a measurable local density.